

**Oxidation of Sulphydril Bodies by Hydrogen Peroxide
at Room Temperatures in Presence of Inorganic
Catalysts. Part I. The Oxidation of Cystine
and Dithioglycollic Acid in Presence of
Tungstic Acid and Molybdic
Acid Sols.**

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The discovery of glutathione by Hopkins (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 286) has created a new interest in the study of the oxidation-reduction mechanism of sulphydril bodies. Ghosh, Roy Chaudhuri and Ganguli (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 43) have shown that in neutral and alkaline medium, a reversible thermodynamic potential is established provided the dithio compound is reduced cathodically at a mercury surface and traces of oxygen are completely eliminated. This observation of Ghosh and co-workers has been confirmed by Brdicka (*Collection*, 1933, 5, 148) by polarographic studies with dropping mercury cathode and Green (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 678) working in Hopkin's laboratory.

Shinohara (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1932, 96, 285) considers that a knowledge of the oxidation mechanism of the sulphydril group to its final stage is essential to an understanding of its biological significance. He studied the oxidation of cystine by iodine and found cysteic acid as the end-product. Warburg (*Biochem. Z.*, 1921, 113, 257) has shown that cystine is oxidised to sulphuric acid, ammonia and carbon dioxide by oxygen with specially prepared charcoal as catalyst. Dakin has carried out a large number of oxidation of substances having biochemical significance by H_2O_2 and has found that the results simulate those observed *in vivo*. Smedley-Maclean and Pearce (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 1252) have similarly carried out the oxidation of oleic acid, by means of hydrogen peroxide. These experiments were all carried out at temperatures above 60°, whereas the life processes occur mostly at temperatures below 40°. We have found that deep seated

oxidation of sulphhydryl bodies by hydrogen peroxide easily takes place at temperatures between 10° to 35° provided suitable catalysts are present. The present paper deals with colloidal sols of tungstic acid and molybdic acid whose behaviour as oxidising catalysts agree in many ways with those of peroxidases.

*Oxidation of Cystine by means of Hydrogen Peroxide
in presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.*

Procedure.—Chemically pure samples of cystine and sodium tungstate were taken, the former dissolved in hydrochloric acid (Merck's 'extra pure') solution and the latter in water. In all the experiments we have used the so-called conductivity water. The experiments were carried out in pyrex conical flasks which were thoroughly cleansed with 20% hydrochloric acid and finally with water. The sol was prepared five to six minutes before the actual experiment was begun by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid to sodium tungstate solution which reacts with hydrochloric acid to form a sol according to the equation

Merck's chemically pure perhydrol was used for preparing each day a fresh solution of hydrogen peroxide. The reaction mixtures were quite stable and no visible turbidity was produced. Three similar flasks, the first containing hydrogen peroxide and sol, the second cystine, hydrogen peroxide and sol, but all having the same p_{H} and same volume, were kept at constant temperature in a thermostat within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ of the required temperature. The first flask indicated that no appreciable amount of hydrogen peroxide was lost due to the spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in the presence of the sol, under the prevailing usual experimental conditions, the second showed the absence of any decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and any reaction without the sol. From the third 0.504 c.c. aliquots were withdrawn at suitable intervals by means of a micropipette and hydrogen peroxide left over was determined by Kingzett's method, 0.01N sodium thiosulphate being used as the titre. The amount of reaction that takes place between the unoxidised cystine and I_2 during the period of titration covering from 5 to 6 minutes is too small to affect the results. Almost all

the experiments were duplicated under conditions as strictly comparable as possible and the same results were obtained.

End products and order of the reaction.—Cysteic acid has been isolated as the main product of oxidation. Ammonia and sulphuric acid in small quantities have also been detected. Cysteic acid is produced according to the following equation,

where R represents $-CH_2 \cdot CHNH_2 \cdot COOH$.

The presence of small quantities of inorganic sulphate and ammonia leads us to assume that the reaction proceeds to some extent beyond the cysteic acid stage according to the following equation,

pyruvic acid being converted into acetic acid and carbon dioxide in presence of excess hydrogen peroxide. We have actually found that ammonia is produced not in the cysteic acid stage of the reaction but at a much later stage.

In order to find out the order of the reaction which was followed till 60% conversion of cystine, we have only taken into account the oxidation of one molecule of cystine by five molecules of hydrogen peroxide, *i.e.*, reaction (1). We have found that our data in each individual experiment fit into the general equation of the first order,

$$K = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{(a - x_1)}{(a - x_2)}$$

where $(a - x_1)$ is the concentration of cystine in molarity corresponding to the time " t_1 " which is generally 4 minutes after starting the reaction, $(a - x_2)$ is the concentration at any time t_2 (in minutes). Concentration of cystine at any time was found from the amount of hydrogen peroxide that disappeared at that time. It is noteworthy, however, that though in each reaction a good unimolecular velocity constant with respect to cystine was obtained, the value of this constant differed for different initial concentrations of cystine.

TABLE I.

Effect of varying the concentration of cystine.

Temp. = 21°. pH, 1.13. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Initial conc. of cystine.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Reaction range selected.	* K (Pseudo 1st order)	
			Limits.	Mean.
0.00417M	0.0878M	(7-60) %	0.0034-0.0031	0.0033
0.00834	0.0898	(7-50)	0.0021-0.0020	0.0021
0.01251	0.0806	(6-62)	0.0019-0.0016	0.0017

When $1/K$ against conc. of cystine is plotted graphically, a straight line is obtained (cf. Fig. 1).

TABLE II.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Temp. = 21°. pH, 1.13. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M.

Initial conc. of H ₂ O ₂	...	0.0247	0.0408	0.0878
K	...	0.0015	0.0021	0.0033

When $1/K$ against $1/\text{conc. of H}_2\text{O}_2$ is plotted graphically, a straight line is obtained (cf. Fig. 2.).

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

* In all the experiments following we have given only the mean value of the constants obtained between the same reaction range,

TABLE III.

*Effect of varying the concentration of sodium tungstate.*Temp. = 21°. p_{H} , 1.13. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M.

Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of Na-tungstate.	K.
0.0455 M	0.0005 M	0.0023
0.0467	0.001	0.0034
0.0461	0.002	0.0055

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the p_{H} .

Temp. = 31°. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Conc. H_2O_2 (M)	... 0.0235	0.0246	0.0246	0.0254	0.0260	0.02578
p_{H}	... 0.92	1.13	1.77	2.5	3.5	5.0
K	... 0.0033	0.0035	0.0025	0.0018	0.0028	0.0048

The p_{H} of the reaction mixtures was gradually increased by the addition of requisite amount of distilled ammonia. Since the product of the reaction is acidic we used at the higher p_{H} 3.5 and 5, acetate buffers at suitable concentrations so that it did not cause any spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the temperature. p_{H} , 1.13. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Temp.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K.
11 °	0.025 M	0.0008
21	0.0247	0.0015
31	0.0246	0.0035

Influence of traces of salts.—The oxidation of cystine by means of hydrogen peroxide does not take place in presence of the following salts, viz., $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$; KCN. But most of them promote the activity of the tungstic acid sol as shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Temp. = 21°. pH, 1.13. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M. Conc. of Na_2WO_4 = 0.0005 M.

Salts.	Conc.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K.
—	—	0.247 M	0.0015
$\text{FeSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$4.07 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.0248	0.0022
$\text{CuSO}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.26×10^{-5}	0.0238	0.0022
$\text{MnCl}_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.05×10^{-4}	0.0239	0.0018
$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4×10^{-4}	0.0239	0.0020
$\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	4×10^{-4}	0.0245	0.0018
KCN	1.04×10^{-3}	0.0247	0.0015

*Oxidation of Cystine by means of Hydrogen Peroxide
in presence of Molybdic Acid Sol.*

Procedure.—Here the experimental procedure is exactly the same as in the case of tungstic acid sol. A sample of ammonium molybdate having the molecular formula $(\text{NH}_4)_6, \text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken. In actual experiments its molecular weight was taken to be equal to one seventh of its true molecular weight corresponding to one atom of molybdenum. The sol was prepared 5 to 6 minutes before the experiment by the addition of HCl to ammonium molybdate, the strength of the former in normality being double the strength of the latter in molarity.

TABLE VII.

Effect of varying the concentration of cystine.

Temp. = 31°. pH, 1.13. Conc. of Am. molybdate = 0.0005 M.

Initial conc. of cystine.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K (unimol. velocity constant with respect to cystine).
0.00417 M	0.07 M	0.00290
0.00834	0.0693	0.00246
0.01251	0.0693	0.00209

The graph of $1/K$ against concentration of cystine is a straight line (cf. Fig. 3).

TABLE VIII.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Temp. = 31°. pH, 1.13. Conc. of Am. molybdate = 0.0005M. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M.

Initial conc. of H ₂ O ₂ (M)	...	0.0234	0.0383	0.07
K	...	0.00183	0.00235	0.00290

When 1/K against 1/conc. of hydrogen peroxide is plotted graphically, a straight line is obtained (cf. Fig. 4).

TABLE IX.

Effect of varying the concentration of ammonium molybdate.

Temp. = 31°. pH, 1.77. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417 M.

Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc of Am. molybdate.	K.
0.0235 M	0.00025 M	0.0018
0.0229	0.0005	0.00324
0.0285	0.001	0.0061

TABLE X.

Effect of varying the pH.

Temp. = 31°. Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M. Conc. of Am. molybdate = 0.0005M.

Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ (M)	...	0.0233	0.0234	0.0229	0.0252	0.0258	0.0258
pH	...	0.92	1.13	1.77	2.5	3.5	5.0
K	...	0.00155	0.00183	0.00324	0.0059	0.0089	0.0115

TABLE XI.

Effect of varying the temperature.

Conc. of cystine = 0.00417M. Conc. of Am. molybdate = 0.0005M.

Temp.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	pH.	K.
21°	0.0234 M	1.13	0.0009
31	0.0234	1.13	0.00183
21	0.0235	1.77	0.0015
31	0.0230	1.77	0.00324

Oxidation of Dithioglycollic Acid by Hydrogen Peroxide in presence of Tungstic Acid Sol.

The oxidation of dithioglycollic acid takes place in exactly the same manner as that of cystine. The sulphhydryl compound is first rapidly converted into its disulphide form in presence of the sol and the dithioglycollic acid is slowly oxidised to sulphoacetic acid as cystine is oxidised to cysteic acid in accordance with the following stoichiometrical equations,

R representing $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COOH}$.

Procedure.—The experimental procedure is similar to that in the case of cystine. The thioglycollic acid solution was freshly prepared everyday. Three pyrex conical flasks, one containing sol and hydrogen peroxide, the second thioglycollic acid and hydrogen peroxide

were taken all having same p_H and same volume. The first did not show any perceptible decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. In the second flask the thioglycollic acid was slowly converted into dithioglycollic acid as determined by an alcoholic iodine solution. In the third vessel the first reaction was very quick and the velocity of the second reaction was measured after the first reaction was over. The amount of hydrogen peroxide left was determined by Kingzett's method.

The velocity was represented by a unimolecular equation of the form,
$$K = \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{(a - x_1)}{(a - x_2)}$$

TABLE XII.

Effect of varying the concentration of thioglycollic acid.

Temp. = 21°. p_H , 2.2. Conc. of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 = 0.001M$.

Initial conc. of thioglycollic acid.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K.
0.00776 M	0.0877M	0.0021
0.01552	0.0891	0.0018
0.0221	0.0865	0.0017

TABLE XIII.

Effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen peroxide.

Temp. = 21°. p_H , 2.2. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.001M.

Conc. of thioglycollic acid.	Initial conc. of H_2O_2 .	K.
0.0079M	0.0238M	0.0016
0.0079	0.0462	0.0018
0.0078	0.0877	0.0021

TABLE XIV.

Effect of varying the concentration of sodium tungstate.

Temp. = 21°. p_H , 2.2.

Conc. of thioglycollic acid.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of Na-tungstate.	K.
0.0078M	0.0452M	0.0005M	0.0011
0.0079	0.0462	0.001	0.0018
0.0079	0.0442	0.002	0.0030

TABLE XV.

Temp. = 21°. p_H , 1.62.

Conc. of thioglycollic acid.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of Na-tungstate.	K.
0.00797M	0.0458M	0.00025M	0.0013
0.00785	0.0456	0.0005	0.0019
0.0078	0.0448	0.001	0.0033
0.0079	0.0461	0.002	0.0060

TABLE XVI.

Effect of varying the p_H .

Temp. = 21°. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Conc. of thioglycollic acid (M) ...	0.00799	0.00785	0.00777	0.00782	0.00793	0.00775	0.00775
Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ (M)	0.0455	0.0456	0.0451	0.0452	0.0445	0.0474	0.0471
p_H ...	1.35	1.62	1.93	2.2	2.4	3.9	5.4
K ...	0.00176	0.0019	0.00156	0.0011	0.00095	0.0019	0.0035

TABLE XVII.

Effect of varying the temperature. p_H , 2.2. Conc. of Na-tungstate = 0.0005M.

Temp.	Conc. of thioglycollic acid.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	K.
11°	0.0078M	0.0465M	0.00047
21	0.0078	0.0452	0.0011
31	0.00786	0.0435	0.0027

DISCUSSION

The oxidation of cystine and dithioglycollic acid by hydrogen peroxide to form respectively cysteic acid and sulphoacetic acid has the following characteristic features :

(1) In presence of tungstic acid sol and molybdic acid sol as catalysts, the reaction takes place quickly at room temperature.

(2) The progress of the reaction in any particular experiment with a definite initial concentration of cystine or dithioglycollic acid can be represented with considerable accuracy by a unimolecular equation provided hydrogen peroxide is present in excess. But unlike the case of true unimolecular reactions, the unimolecular constant is not independent of the initial concentration of the reductant but diminishes as the initial concentration of the reductant increases.

(3) The unimolecular velocity constant increases as the initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide increases.

(4) In the case of the molybdic acid sol as catalyst, the velocity concentration continually increases as the p_H of the medium increases from 1 to 5. Beyond p_H 5, hydrogen peroxide undergoes slow spontaneous decomposition and therefore the optimum condition could not be determined.

(5) In the case of the tungstic acid sol as catalyst, the velocity constant between p_H 1—2.5 has an optimum value at p_H 1.13 for cystine and at p_H 1.62 for dithioglycollic acid. But as the p_H is increased from 2.5 to 3.5 the velocity constant again increases and continues to increase up to p_H 5. Beyond this hydrogen peroxide undergoes perceptible spontaneous decomposition and therefore the second optimum p_H could not be determined.

(6) For each 10° rise in temperature the velocity constants increase about 2—2.3 times.

(7) The following salts [$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$] in very low concentrations do not decompose hydrogen peroxide but they promote the catalytic activity of tungstic acid sol.

(8) Potassium cyanide has no influence on the catalytic activity of the sol indicating that the sol as such and not impurities like iron salts present in traces in the sol, is the active catalytic agent.

(9) As the stoichiometric concentration of the sol is increased, the velocity constant of the reaction increases but not in exact proportion to the increase in the concentration of the sol. This indicates that the active surface of the sol, does not increase in proportion to its increase of stoichiometric concentration. The particle size increases with increase in the concentration of the tungstate and molybdate used for sol formation and hence the specific surface or the ratio $\frac{\text{active surface}}{\text{mass}}$ diminishes.

The peculiarities noted in section (2) and (3) above can be explained by the following mechanism of reaction:—

The reaction only takes place between the molecules of reductant and hydrogen peroxide actually adsorbed on the surface of the sol. We assume further that for equivalent concentrations, the adsorption coefficient of cystine is the same as that of cysteic acid and that of dithioglycollic acid is the same as that of sulphoacetic acid. The portion of the sol surface covered jointly by cystine and cysteic acid or by dithioglycollic acid

and sulphoacetic acid remains, therefore, constant throughout the progress of the reaction in a particular experiment and the fraction depends only on the initial concentration of the reductant. Let a_1 be the fraction of the sol surface covered by the reductant and the oxidised product together, when the initial concentration of the reductant is c_1 . Then at any time during the progress of the reaction the fraction of the surface covered by the reductant is $a_1 \frac{(c_1 - x)}{c_1}$ and the fraction covered by the oxidation product is

$\frac{a_1 x}{c_1}$ where x is the concentration of the reductant oxidised in time " t ". If a' is the fraction of the surface area covered by molecules of hydrogen peroxide, and if the velocity of reaction is proportional to the product of the surface concentrations of the reductant and of hydrogen peroxide, then

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_3 \cdot a' \cdot \bar{a}_1 \frac{c_1 - x}{c_1} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

But according to Langmuir's ideas

$$a_1 = \frac{K_1 c_1}{K_2 + K_1 c_1} \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{K' c'}{K'' + K' c'}$$

where c_1 is the initial concentration in solution of the reductant and c' is the concentration of hydrogen peroxide. If, as in our experiments the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is always in excess, c' may be considered to be constant throughout the course of the reaction. Hence

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_3 \cdot \frac{K' c'}{K'' + K' c'} \cdot \frac{K_1 c_1}{K_2 + K_1 c_1} \cdot \frac{c_1 - x}{c_1} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$\text{or} \quad K_3 \cdot \frac{K' c'}{K'' + K' c'} \cdot \frac{K_1}{K_2 + K_1 c_1} = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{c_1}{c_1 - x} = K \quad (\text{Experimental}$$

value as given in tables)

... (iii)

If c' , i.e., the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is in excess the experimental value of the unimolecular velocity constant K will depend on the value of c_1 , the initial concentration of the reductant. K will diminish as c_1 increases, and it follows from (iii) that $1/K$

plotted against c_1 will be a straight line. This has been verified (*cf.* Figs. 1 and 3).

Again for the same initial concentration of reductant c_1 , the value of the unimolecular constant K will depend on the value of c , the concentration of hydrogen peroxide. In fact, unlike the previous case, the value of K will increase as the concentration of hydrogen peroxide increases. According to Equation (iii)

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{1}{K_3} \left[\frac{K_2 + K_1 c_1}{K_1} \right] \left[\frac{K''}{K'c'} + 1 \right]$$

i.e., for constant value of c_1 , the reciprocal of the observed velocity constant plotted against the reciprocal of the concentration of hydrogen peroxide will be a straight line. This has also been verified (*vide* Figures 2 and 4).

